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Design of a compact 140 MeV electron linear accelerator

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ABSTRACT

In this deliverable we report about the different accelerators facilities and accelerators technologies that could provide a Very High Energy Electron (VHEE) beam with energies in the range of 50-200 MeV to be used in Radiobiology studies first and in pre-clinical studies for radiotherapy after. Special attention will be paid to one of the major challenges for VHEE: the FLASH delivery modality, consisting of an ultra-short high dose-rate, possibly over a large area, providing a uniform dose distribution throughout the target.

ARIES Consortium, 2020

For more information on ARIES, its partners and contributors please see <http://aries.web.cern.ch>

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. Introduction..... 5

2. State of the art of the VHEE RT..... 6

2.1 VHEE RT..... 6

2.2 FLASH VHEE RT10

3. Accelerators and Accelerator technologies for VHEE RT..... 11

3.1 VHEE ACCELERATOR FACILITIES11

 3.1.1 Normal Conducting RF linac11

 3.1.2 Super Conducting RF linac15

 3.1.3 Laser Plasma Facilities15

3.2 NOVEL ACCELERATOR TECHNOLOGIES FOR VHEE APPLICATIONS17

 19

4. Possible designs for a compact electron linear accelerator for VHEE applications..... 20

4.1 S-BAND LINACS20

4.2 C-BAND LINACS.....23

4.3 X-BAND LINACS.....24

5. Conclusion and Perspectives 26

6. References 28

Executive summary

Cancer is a critical societal issue. Worldwide, in 2018 alone, 18.1 million cases were diagnosed, 9.6 million people died and 43.8 million people were living with cancer. RT is a fundamental component of effective cancer treatment and control. RT has progressed rapidly with the development of new technologies and innovation leading to remarkable improvements in every phase of RT. But from the point of view of accelerator technologies and the use of different particles either than photons or protons remains rather conventional. In this sense the use of Very High Energy Electron (VHEE) in the range of 50–200 MeV offers a very promising option for anticancer Radiation Therapy (RT). In some aspects as the dosimetry and the ballistic could surpass the photons, which are currently the most commonly used in standard RT. Nowadays different accelerator technologies as the High-Gradient Normal Conducting RF (NCRF) or even the novel accelerator techniques such as Laser Plasma Accelerator (LPA) are possible candidates for the VHEE RT.

After introducing the motivations and main parameters for VHEE, the particular case of FLASH therapy is introduced and described.

The existing facilities for VHEE are presented, and recent technological developments with an impact on the design of future VHEE facilities are introduced.

The main parameters and the indicative layout of future VHEE accelerators for radiation therapy corresponding to three frequency bands are presented and discussed.

1. Introduction

Establishing innovative treatment modalities for cancer is a major 21st century health challenge. With the recent development of High-Gradient Normal Conducting RF linac technology or even the novel accelerator techniques such as Laser Plasma Accelerator (LPA), Very High Energy Electron (VHEE) in the range 50–200 MeV offer a very promising option for anticancer Radiation Therapy (RT). Theoretically, the ballistic and dosimetry properties of VHEE surpass those of photons, which are currently the most commonly used in standard RT. In particular, they show the following advantages:

- A significant decrease of integral dose to healthy tissues or sensitive organs compared to photons.
- High dose-rates and fast electromagnetic scanning provide a uniform dose distribution throughout the target and allow for unforeseen RT modalities in particular FLASH high-dose rate.
- More compact and less expensive facilities than the one used in proton therapy.

For achieving these aims, a synergistic and multidisciplinary research effort based on accelerator technology as well as physical and radiobiological comparisons to see how well VHEE can meet the current assumptions and become a clinical reality is needed. From the point of view of the accelerator technology the ARIES project is the ideal framework.

All this asks in a first stage for a large beam test activity, in order to experimentally characterize VHEE beams and their ability to produce the FLASH effect, and provide a test bed for the associated technologies. It is also important to compare the properties of the electron beams depending on the way they are produced, (NC RF linac or LPA technologies). In a second stage these results will guide the conceptual designs of new VHEE-RT facilities. A preliminary design study has been reported in MS-15 [1].

2. State of the art of the VHEE RT

2.1 VHEE RT

Cancer is a critical societal issue. Worldwide, in 2018 alone, 18.1 million cases were diagnosed, 9.6 million people died. Current projections anticipate an increase, with approximately 27.5 million newly diagnosed patients and 16.3 million related deaths per year by 2040 and become the leading cause of death (Figures 1 and 2). Cancer imposes an *enormous economic burden worldwide*—around 2 trillion dollars in 2010 and these costs are rising and putting a major burden on public healthcare budgets. In the EU where over 3.7 million new cases per year are diagnosed and total costs over 120 billion EUR were reported for the EU in 2012 [26, 27, 29].

Figure 1: Global Cancer Mortality

Figure 2: Predicted Global Cancer cases

Radiotherapy is a fundamental component of effective cancer treatment and control. It is estimated that about half of all cancer patients would benefit from radiotherapy for treatment of localised disease, local control, and palliation. More than 10,000 electron linear accelerators (linacs) are currently used worldwide to treat patients. Typically these linacs operate in the low beam energy range of 5-15 MeV. In most cases the electrons are used to produce photons through bremsstrahlung in high-density (e.g., tungsten) targets and it is the resulting photon beam that is then used for therapy. However, **conventional photon RT** is characterised by almost exponential attenuation and absorption, and consequently delivers the maximum energy near the beam entrance, but continues to deposit significant energy at distances beyond the cancer target (Figure 3). The maximum dose for photons beams with an energy of about 8 MeV, is reached at a depth of 2–3cm of soft tissue. Exit doses can be as high as 50% of the dose to the target resulting in considerable damage to healthy tissue.

To compensate for these disadvantages of photons beams and to better target the radiation dose distribution to the shape of the tumours, RT has progressed rapidly with the development of new technologies and innovation leading to remarkable improvements in every phase of RT, related to treatment - from simulation to planning, to delivery, with the aim to tailor treatment to the specific anatomy of individual patients.

Figure 3: Dose profile for various particle beams in water (beam widths $r=0.5$ cm)

The fundamental step towards **high-precision RT** was brought by technological advances in techniques of **image guided beam** delivery utilizing conventional clinical dose rates (0.1 – 0.2 Gy/s) and have provided physicians with their best options for improving this critical tool in cancer care, allowing the ability to preferentially target tumors while minimizing the collateral dose to the *surrounding normal tissues*.

Despite all these advances, the treatment of many primary and metastatic tumors however remains

a challenge as the **therapeutic window** between tumor eradication and normal tissue complications is **narrow**. For instance, in the brain, stereotactic radiosurgery has provided the greatest increase in therapeutic index for treating limited brain metastases but still remains suboptimal for most patients with primary brain tumors.

RT with heavier charged particles, also called **hadron therapy** (HT) with protons and other ions species has also been proposed and offers several ballistic advantages over the classical RT with X-rays. Not only do hadrons and particles deposit most of their energy at the end of their range, but also the particle beam can be shaped with great precision (Figure 3). This allows for **more accurate tumour treatment**, destroying the cancer cells more precisely with less damage to surrounding tissues. RT using the unique physical and radiobiological properties of charged hadrons also allows for more highly conformal treatment of various kinds of tumours, including those that are radio-resistant. These findings opened many research perspectives. However, despite the recent progress of HT, numerous challenges and new opportunities are yet to be addressed to maximize clinical outcomes and cost-effectiveness of this advanced therapy modality in order to make it: (a) applicable for treating **larger number of tumours**, (b) accessible for a **greater number of patients** globally.

Now, more than 70 years after the initial idea of using proton and heavier ion therapy, HT has eventually reached the critical time of transitioning from a limited number of specialized institutions to many particle- therapy centres worldwide. Currently, **proton therapy** is flourishing with around 70 HT facilities in the clinical practice and many are under construction or planning. These centres are treating selected tumour patients where radiation damage with X-rays to the surrounding normal tissue could be harmful such as tumours at the base of the skull or tumours in young children. By the end of 2018, over 160.000 patients were treated with protons world-wide [18, 28, 30].

Proton-therapy technology has become significantly more compact today but once combined with the gantry and other equipment needed, even the most compact systems for sale today occupy a couple of hundred square metres. This is much larger than a conventional treatment room of 50 square metres and most hospitals lack the financial resources and space to construct a special building for proton therapy. Currently few patients have access to such treatment mainly confined to the geographic areas in which particle therapy is or will be available. The solution is either to make proton-therapy facilities smaller and cheaper, with costs of around 5-10 million for a single room, *similar to the state-of-the-art photon systems* and/or look at **possible alternatives**

A **most interesting and unexplored** possibility is the use of RT with **higher energy electrons**. Although, *low-energy electron (LEE)* have historically been used to treat cancer for more than five decades, but mostly for the treatment of superficial tumours given their very *limited penetration depth*. However, this limitation can be overcome if the electron energy is increased as can be seen in Figure 3. It shows the dose profile for various particle beams in water and for electrons at 200 MeV the penetration becomes deeper and the transverse penumbra sharper, though the longitudinal penumbra is also increased but this can be reduced by focusing the electrons (Figure 4). While the use of high energy electron beams (up to 50 MeV) has been already studied in the 80's by the Karolinska group [6] their clinical implementation was not continued. More recently, the idea of investigating the use of **very high-energy (50-200 MeV) electron (VHEE)** beams for RT has gained interest. This most interesting and unexplored possibility is being studied by many research groups from the most diverse extractions, from clinical to biology, from accelerator physics to dosimetry. This topic has been the subject of the *VHEE 2020 International Workshop*, which took place virtually on the 5-7 October 2020, [<https://indico.cern.ch/event/939012/>] and organized by CERN and by the author of this report in the framework of the ARIES WP3 activity. More than 400 scientists from the most diverse extractions gathered virtually to evaluate and discuss the perspectives of this novel technique. Such workshop followed up a similar one organized in 2017 in Daresbury [<https://www.cockcroft.ac.uk/events/VHEE17/>] and the large increase in attendance shows the vitality and increasing interest in the field. The workshop included also a very lively session dedicated to industrial partners.

Figure 4: Focusing of e-beams (courtesy of A. Lagzda).

The main *advantages of VHEE beams* over photons are related to the fact that 1) small diameter VHEE beams can be scanned and focused easily (Figure 4), thereby producing finer resolution for intensity modulated treatments than photon beams. Under certain conditions, only small sensitivity to tissue heterogeneity unlike protons can be achieved [34, 35, 36]. This represents a *new prospect for increasing the therapeutic index of radiation therapy that is dependent on spatial dose distribution*. 2) accelerators may be constructed at significantly **lower cost** compared to the current installations

required for protons beam delivery and presents an interesting and possibly cost-effective option to

treat cancer. 3) VHEE beam operate at very high dose rate, possibly compatible with the generation of the “FLASH effect” (*i.e.* to elicit normal tissue sparing), described further below.

Figure 5: CLIC RF X-band cavity prototype (12 GHz, 100 MV/m)

Today and after 3 decades of research in linear colliders on the Japanese Linear Collider (JLC) [2], the Next Linear Collider (NLC) [4] and the Compact Linear Collider (CLIC) [3,4] (Figure 5), it is possible to have **compact high-gradient linacs** (~100 MV/m), which make a compact VHEE radiation therapy accelerator a reality. A considerable research and development program has been carried out in order to obtain the demanding performances of CLIC linac: an accelerating gradient of 100 MV/m, low breakdown rate, micron-tolerance alignment and a high RF-to-beam efficiency (around 30%). Furthermore, a complementary program to establish the design process, manufacturing technology and operational algorithms for the accelerating structures of the CLIC main linacs has been carried out in parallel [12-14, 32-33]. An important milestone has now been achieved with the successful high-gradient operation of numerous X-band accelerating structure prototypes at gradients above 100 MV/m. An experimental test facility called CERN Linear Electron Accelerator for Research (CLEAR) [17] has been developed using these latest advances providing high-energy 50-250 MeV and high-charge beam necessary to deliver VHEE and FLASH therapy (Figure 6).

Figure 6: CLEAR User Facility for VHEE Studies

All this is being applied in the conceptual designs of new RT facilities, such as the one jointly being developed by CHUV and CERN [<https://home.cern/news/news/knowledge-sharing/cern-and-lausanne-university-hospital-collaborate-pioneering-new-cancer>].

Furthermore, the use of novel accelerator techniques such as **Laser Plasma Accelerator** is also starting to be applied in the VHEE field. These are currently the subject of a wide international study and in particular we highlight the EU network: EUPRAXIA [15] and also in ARIES. Even some experimental tests have been carried out with laser-plasma sources at ELBE-DRACO in HZDR [23-25] and in the LOA in the Institut Polytechnique de Paris [48] and the SCAPA facility [16] in the University of Strathclyde.

2.2 FLASH VHEE RT

FLASH-RT has recently caused tremendous excitement in the radio-oncology field as it may revolutionize modern day RT. Supported by radiobiological studies, FLASH-RT is a paradigm-shifting method for delivering doses within an extremely **short irradiation time** (tenths of a second) and **Ultra High Dose rate** (UHD mean dose rate above **100 Gy/s**) in the pulse. FLASH-RT has been shown to preserve normal tissue in various species (mice, pig, cat, zebrafish) and various organs (brain, lung, gut, skin, hematopoietic system) **while still** maintaining anti-tumor efficacy equivalent to conventional RT at the same dose level when delivered in a single fraction or hypo-fractionated [37]. This effect has been called the “FLASH effect” and involves in part, a decreased production of toxic reactive oxygen species (Fig. 6). Noteworthy too is the fact that the “FLASH effect” was and continues to be defined in vivo, a feature that portends its rapid clinical implementation and utility.

Figure 7: Iso-efficacy of FLASH-RT and conventional dose-rate (CONV) irradiation was observed by tumor-growth delay assessment of U87 human GBM xenografted tumors while there is a significant reduction in normal tissue toxicity (NTCP) measured using neurocognitive impairment using Novel object recognition (NOR) assay after FLASH-RT compared to CONV-RT. From Bourhis et al, 2019 [6].

Although most FLASH studies to date were performed with 5.5 MeV **electron** beams from the Kinetron linac in the Institute Curie at Orsay and the eRt6-Oriatron linac at CHUV [37, 41], it has also been reported at ESRF with **synchrotron X-rays** [42] and more recently with **proton beams** [43,44] In addition, several studies, reporting absence of the FLASH effect, are also becoming available with synchrotron [45], proton [46] and electron [47] beams. Although performed at high dose rate, these studies might have been outside the searched parameter window. This evidence emphasizes the necessity of carefully defined, controlled and documented experimental conditions

(both physical and biological parameters) to ensure the possibility to reproduce and compare experimental results as well as the safe and reliable transfer of these strategies into the clinic. Important knowledge will have to be generated using the various facilities that are becoming available for R&D in this topic. This innovative and clinically relevant research provide a fantastic opportunity to work in multidisciplinary teams.

However, the **potential advantage** of using **electron beams** lays in the intrinsically higher dose that can potentially be reached compared to protons and photons, especially over large areas as would be needed for large tumours. Most of the preclinical data demonstrating the increased therapeutic index of FLASH has been using a single fraction and hypo-fractionated regimen of RT and using 4 to 6 MeV beams, that do not allow to treat deep seated tumours and trigger large lateral penumbra. This problem can be solved by increasing the electron energy to values higher than 50 MeV, where the penetration depth is larger. The High-Gradient linac technology advances for VHEE lead by CLIC collaboration were happening at the same time as pioneering preliminary work on FLASH was carried out by key researchers from CHUV and Curie Institute.

3. Accelerators and Accelerator technologies for VHEE RT

As stated in section 2, preliminary **VHEE experimental** studies has been realized using **NC accelerator facilities** in NLTCA at SLAC and CLEAR at CERN, giving very promising results for the use of VHEE electron beams. Furthermore some experimental tests have been carried out with **laser-plasma sources** at ELBE-DRACO in HZDR and in LOA in IPP. In particular for the **FLASH**, experimental studies have been realized at low-energies with the Kinetron linac in the Institute Curie at Orsay and the eRt6-Oriatron linac at CHUV and at very high-energies at CLEAR at CERN.

In the following we will describe in section 3.1 some accelerator facilities that are available nowadays or in the near future to perform VHEE studies. In section 3.2 we will report about novel accelerator technologies that could be applied for future VHEE facilities.

3.1 VHEE ACCELERATOR FACILITIES

3.1.1 Normal Conducting RF linac

NC RF linac is the technology being used for most of the VHEE research. The main advantages of the linacs are the flexibility and compactness.

The current and next future available machines for VHEE experiments are:

eRT6-Oriatron at CHUV is a prototype 6 MeV electron linac [45] producing pulsed electron beams at a mean dose-rate ranging from 0.1 Gy/s (i.e. conventional RT dose-rate) up to 100 Gy/s, corresponding to a dose, in each electron pulse, ranging from 0.01 up to 10 Gy. The prescribed dose for FLASH irradiations is determined according to the system used (chemical, cells, zebrafishes, brain of mouse).

Figure 8: Oriatron linac

ElectronFlash at IC is a S-band (3 GHz) NC electron linac developed by La Sapienza for FLASH-IORT (Intra Operative Radiation Therapy) applications. The electron beam has an energy range of 6-12 MeV, 1 mA beam current, pulse length of 2 us at 10-100Hz with a dose per pulse of 0.01-0.1 Gy and dose rate of 10-20 Gy/min. An upgrade to C-band technology (5.712 GHz) for compactness and higher current (100 mA) is in progress.

Detailed info in:

https://indico.cern.ch/event/939012/contributions/4039403/attachments/2118039/3563950/Faillaces_VHEE_Talk_-_v2.pdf

CLEAR at CERN is an electron NC linac located in the experimental area of the CLIC Test Facility 3 (CTF3) at CERN. The linac is capable of producing an electron beam with an energy 50-250 MeV, bunch charge 0.01-0.4 nC, transverse normalized emittance 3/30 um for 0.05/0.5 nC, relative energy spread < 0.2%, bunch length 200-1200 um, repetition rate 1-5 Hz (25 with an upgrade), number of bunches 1 -150 with 1.5 GHz of micro bunch spacing [14]. The beam line includes transport and focusing elements, an experimental area currently used to test CLIC two-beam modules, and a complete set of beam diagnostics, including spectrometers before and after the experimental area [35] (Figure 7). A dedicated beam line for VHEE experiments is under study (ex: larger quadrupole aperture) that could also be a test prototype for a larger clinical machine. Detailed info in: https://indico.cern.ch/event/939012/contributions/3971716/attachments/2116371/3561174/CLEAR_for_Radiotherapy_Research.pdf

Figure 9: the CLEAR facility for VHEE testing

To carry out the technology development for CLIC, a broad collaboration, including groups working on many different applications has been established.

In particular for medical applications, a FLASH facility based on a CLIC X-band 100 MeV linac is being designed in collaboration with CHUV to treat large, deep-seated tumors in FLASH conditions. The facility is as compact as to fit on a typical hospital campus (Figure 8).

Detailed info in:

https://indico.cern.ch/event/939012/contributions/3971723/attachments/2116578/3561586/VHEE_workshop_wuensch_2020-10-6.pdf

Figure 10: FLASH facility for CHUV.

Figure 11: The CLARA Facility

CLARA at Daresbury, CLARA Phase 1 is a NC linac providing 40 MeV, 10 Hz, 100 pC e-beam. CLARA Phase 2 will provide a source of electrons at clinically relevant energies up to 250 MeV for R&D in VHEE - plasmid and cell irradiation, dosimetry, treatment planning. A dedicated beam exploitation area: FEBE (Full Energy Beam Exploitation) has been designed taking into account experience of both completed and planned VHEE experiments on CLARA Phase 1, with flexibility and diagnostic capabilities (bunch charge, beam position, transverse and longitudinal profile

diagnostics in the arc and the hutch beamline). It will provide an ideal test-bed for future VHEE studies. Furthermore potential in-air VHEE experiments have been considered during the design. FEBE design and procurement is planned to be completed in 2020 in readiness to install during shutdown in 2021/22, with first “Proof-of-principle”, “High Impact” experiments expected in 2023.

Detailed info in:

https://indico.cern.ch/event/939012/contributions/3971722/attachments/2116467/3561358/VHEE20_CLARA_Angal-Kalinin.pdf

Figure 12: The AWA electron linac.

AWA at ANL is a NC electron linac with an energy range between 6-63 MeV, bunch charge 0.1-100 nC, transverse normalized emittance 0.5/240 μm , bunch length 0.1-3 mm, repetition rate 0.5-10 Hz, with the possibility of longitudinal shaping (train, tringle, rectangle and trapezoid). Beamline with large chambers to host structures, Be window for moderate vacuum, several DUT test area, measurement of charge, power, energy, beam shape, emittance and bunch length and shielding room to improve signal-to-noise ratio are available.

Detailed info in:

https://indico.cern.ch/event/939012/contributions/4047839/attachments/2117937/3566410/AWA_VHEE20_Jing.pdf

3.1.2 Super Conducting RF linac

ELBE Center of High Power Radiation Sources at **HZDR**: Superconducting RF linac with maximum 40 MeV energy (50 MeV with RF pulsing), bunch charge 0.01-80 pC, repetition rate from single pulse up to 13 MHz, macro pulse length 0.1 ms-CW, transverse normalized emittance $< 15 \mu\text{m}$.

Figure 13: The ELBE SRF linac

Detailed info in:

https://indico.cern.ch/event/939012/contributions/3971810/attachments/2117931/3563768/Schram_VHEE2020_ELBE.pdf

PITZ at DESY in Zeuthen is a photoinjector capable of producing an electron beam with an energy of 7 MeV. It can offer a bunch pattern with customized time structure: bunch trains of up to 1ms length and bunch repetition rate within train (0.1 - 1 MHz, optimum 4.5 MHz). Trains can be repeated with up to 10 Hz: from 1 to 1000 bunches in 1 ms (optimum up to 4500) and from 1 to 10 000 bunches in 1 s (optimum up to 45 000). Depending on bunch charge, individual bunches can have: length of 0.1- 60 ps (bunch compressor) and spot size down to $\sim 100\mu\text{m}$. An energy upgrade up to 250 MeV is foreseen by means of a SC XFEL type cryomodule.

Detailed info in:

https://indico.cern.ch/event/939012/contributions/3971737/attachments/2116469/3561361/FLASH_RT_RD_options_at_PITZ_final.pdf

3.1.3 Laser Plasma Facilities

Figure 14: Charge profile in function of the energy for the laser Wakefield electron acceleration in the multi MeV range in ELBE.

DRACO at **ELBE** Center of High Power Radiation Sources at **HZDR** is a 1 PW Laser system providing 50-400 MeV electrons with up to 500 pC bunch charge, 10 fs pulse length, 5 mrad divergence and 1 Hz repetition rate.

Detailed info in:

https://indico.cern.ch/event/939012/contributions/3971810/attachments/2117931/3563768/Schramm_VHEE2020_ELBE.pdf

Figure 15: LOA laser driven wakefield electron accelerator

LOA at **IPP** is a Laser driven wakefield plasma electron acceleration delivering an electron beam with a maximum energy in the range of 100 -150 MeV, depending on laser depletion and with a maximum charge in the range of 10 pC to few nC depending on injection mechanism and on saturation of the accelerating structure. A beamline dedicated to medical applications known as IDRA is being constructed. The new beamline will provide stable experimental conditions for radiobiology and dosimetry R&D.

Detailed info in:

<https://indico.cern.ch/event/939012/contributions/3971739/attachments/2116620/3561684/Flacco-VHEE-2020.pdf>

For completeness the performances of some of these machines are summarized in Table 1.

Low-Energy beam parameters		
	eRT6-ORIATRON @ CHUV	
Treatment	Zebrafish embryo	Brain of Mice
Energy (MeV)	6	6
Field size (cm)	Water tank	1.7
SSD (cm)	65	75.5 / 34
Delivered dose (Gy)	12	10
Pulse length (us)	1.8	1.8
Pulse dose (Gy)	12	1 / 10
Repetition rate (Hz)	100	100
Number of pulses	1	10 / 1
Irradiation time (ms)	0.018	90 / 0.018

Beam time availability	Now	Now	
In vitro / In vivo	Yes / Yes	Yes / Yes	
High-Energy beam parameters			
	CLEAR @ CERN	ELBE @ HZDR	DRACO @ HZDR
Energy (MeV)	60 - 220	15-36 (CW) 15-50 (RF pulsed)	100-400
Energy spread (MeV)	< 1 (FWMH)	< 0,1 (FWHM)	10% (FWHM)
Bunch charge (nC)	0.01 - 0.4	0,01 - 0,08	< 0.5
Bunch length (ps)	0.2-10	0.5-5	0.01
Normalized emittances (um)	3-30 (charge dependent)	<15	~1
Repetition rate (Hz)	0.8 - 5 (25 upgrade)	< 13MHz (CW)	1
Number of micro-bunches in train	1- >150	CW	1
Micro-bunch spacing	1.5	>77 ns	-
Beam time availability	Now	Now	Now
In vitro / In vivo	Yes / No	Yes / Yes	Yes / Yes

Table 1: Beam performances of low-energy and high energy facilities.

3.2 NOVEL ACCELERATOR TECHNOLOGIES FOR VHEE APPLICATIONS

Recent advances in accelerator technology, especially in the high-gradient RF structures where more than 100 MeV/m are now achievable in the lab environment are transforming the landscape for VHEE RT.

VHEE RT requires beam energies between 50-200 MeV, an improved dose conformity and scale to higher doses rates, in the case of the FLASH-RT until 50 Gy/s are needed. Novel high gradient technologies could enable ultra-compact structures, with higher repetition rates and higher currents.

An international R&D global effort is being made by labs such as CERN, INFN, KEK, MIT, UCLA, LANL, SLAC and industry partners and focused towards the

- Material origin and purity, surface treatments, manufacturing technology
- Consistency and reproducibility of test results.

Some promising R&D are:

- The **distributed coupling accelerator** developed at SLAC [49].

Figure 16: X-band π -mode Distributed Coupling RF structures

- The use of **cryogenic copper** is transforming the linac design offering a new frontier from beam brightness, efficient and cost-capability. Operation at 77 K (liquid nitrogen) results in a minor decrease in efficiency for establishing gradient with a dramatic reduction in cost and increase in performance. Experiments have shown: increased conductivity and hardness enabling higher gradients, increase in Q_0 by a factor of 2.5 and in consequence 2.5 less power to establish gradient allowing for heavy beam loading even at high gradient resulting with the improvement of the system efficiency (Figure 10). High-power cryogenics X-band structures have been realized to confirm the RF performance and to measure the breakdown rates, 150 MeV are already demonstrated in lab conditions [50].

Figure 17: Left: Breakdown probability measurement in a single cell cryogenic test. Right: Quality factor for cryogenic copper accelerator structures

- Another approach for the next generation of compact, efficient and high performance VHEE accelerator is the use of **higher frequencies millimetric waves** (~100 GHz) and **higher repetition rates** using THz sources. Table 2 shows a comparison of X-band linacs and mm-wave linac parameters.

	X-band linac	mm-Wave linac
Frequency	11.424 GHz	100 GHz
Shunt impedance	430 MΩ/m	1 GΩ/m
Structure length	1.16 m	0.5 m

Table 2: Comparison of X-band and mm-wave linac parameters.

Different structures at 110 GHz have been built and tested to 230 MV/m gradients with split cell and diffusion bonding at SLAC (Figure 11).

Figure 18: Built and tested structures to 230 MeV.

High-Power testing of 110 GHz accelerating structures are also ongoing in MIT, using a laser-triggered semiconductor switch for pulse shaping. More in detail, short tunable pulse lengths of few-100s nanoseconds with quasi-optical coupling are demonstrated on high power setup. Gradients of 225 MeV/m (<100k pulses) are achieved but breakdowns have been observed after the power increased and rapidly process away (Figure 12). MIT is improving the transport, coupling and diagnostics. Now they are approaching the 600 kW and upgrades are planned to 800 kW [51].

Figure 19: Left: Laser-triggered semiconductor switch for pulse shaping. Right: Measures and simulated gradient from transmitted pulse.

- Finally, **relativistic electron sources** with charges of 160 nC delivered in 1 second, with high repetition rate (ultimately 400Hz) utilizing field emission (100 fC per bunch, 40 ns pulse) are being developed by SLAC NSF program. An electron source as well as the associated

diagnostics suitable to determine emittance, energy spread and inform modeling of transport, is in fabrication and will be commissioned during fall of '20. An active pulse shaping and compression R&D is also ongoing with a gyrotron CW source with pulse shaping at AFRL (Air Force Research Laboratory).

Figure 20: Left: Relativistic electron source. Right: Commissioning device for relativistic electron source.

Detailed info in:

https://indico.cern.ch/event/939012/contributions/3971198/attachments/2115572/3559552/VHEE_2020_Nanni_Post.pdf

4. Possible designs for a compact electron linear accelerator for VHEE applications

In view of the current accelerator technologies described in Section 3, different possible High-Gradient (HG) compact accelerating structures could be used to deliver electrons beams at ~140 MeV energy for VHEE applications and with intensities as high as to cope with the FLASH dose delivery. In this section we will describe only linacs where normal conducting RF is being used.

4.1 S-BAND LINACS

A detailed optics design and beam dynamics simulations for a facility dedicated to VHEE radiobiology experiments using a **S-band NC HG linac** in the energy range of 70-140 MeV has been studied in the framework of the PRAE (Platform for Research and Applications with Electrons) project at Orsay [7, 20-21]. This has also been reported in some extension in “Medical applications of high-energy electron beams [1]. A schematic view of this facility is shown in Figure 21 and the main performances are summarized in Table 3.

Figure 21: PRAE Accelerator Layout, with quotations in mm. The HG-NC S-band linac is indicated by the cyan box.

Parameters	
Energy	70 – 140 [MeV]
Charge (variable)	0.00005 – 2 [nC]
Normalized emittance	3-10 [mm mrad]
RF frequency	3.0 [GHz]
Repetition rate	50 [Hz]
Bunch length, rms	< 10 [psec]
Energy spread, rms	< 0.2 %
Bunches per pulse	1

Table 3: PRAE accelerator performances.

The PRAE accelerator consists of a photo-injector, an acceleration section and two beam lines with the corresponding experimental setups: the subatomic physics in the direct line and the instrumentation and radiobiology platform sharing the deviated line, as shown in Figure 21. The RF gun is located on the left of this figure. The cyan box shows the first HG linac. After the linac, a quadrupole doublet is used to focus the beam. A drift space of about 4 meters is left for a second HG linac which can boost the electron energy to 140 MeV in future. A quadrupole triplet is used to confine the beam as well as allowing to measure the beam emittance. After the triplet, a dogleg with two 30° dipole magnets (pink boxes) are used to deviate the beam following the building constrains and providing a

separated area for the radiobiology experiments. Between the dipoles three quadrupoles are used to match the dispersion and beta function. Finally, another quadrupole triplet is used to achieve the beam requirements for the Grid mini-beams and FLASH modalities. The detailed technical description of the different components could be found in [21], in the following we described in detail the HG S-band compact linac.

The HG-NC S-band linac for the PRAE linac is a Travelling Wave (TW), quasi-constant gradient section with coupling cells designed to maintain maximum field symmetry and efficient power coupling. The structure will operate at 3 GHz (30 °C in vacuum) in the $2\pi/3$ mode. The RF design consists of 97-cells (95 regular cells + 2 coupling cells), with a length of 3.47 m, see Figure

Figure 22: 3D design with CST for PRAE HG accelerating structure.

22 [52]. Such structure will provide an energy gain of 65 MeV for an input peak power of 30 MW. The structure has been fabricated by Research Instruments [53]. A layout with the structure on the girder showing the dual power splitter is shown in Figure 23.

Figure 23: Layout of the PRAE HG TW accelerating structure with the dual power splitter.

All components have been made from OFHC copper. The cavity has been joined by high temperature brazing processes. The iris shape is optimized to reduce peak electric fields but to maintain the overall group velocity variation and filling time characteristic. In order to preserve a low beam emittance, the in- and out-coupling cells have a symmetric power feed and a racetrack shape of the cell. The symmetric layout cancels the dipole component of the fields in the coupling cell and in addition the racetrack shape is designed such that also quadrupolar components decay. All RF surfaces will be machined with diamond tooling leading to minimized surface roughness, highest quality factor and low field emission.

The low-power RF tests performed in RI (Figure 24) have shown the expected performances.

Figure 24: Tuning of the PRAE HG TW Accelerating Structure at RI.

The structure has been delivered last September 2020 at the IJClab for the High-Power testing on site. Unfortunately, being the PRAE project cancelled the tests has been postponed and the future location of the structure is not decided.

In a different context but using the same kind of HG-NC Accelerating structures fabricated by RI and with similar RF-gun linac configuration, the linear accelerator ARES (Accelerator Research Experiment) at SINBAD (Short Innovative Bunches and Accelerators at DESY) has reached on 28th October 2020 155 MeV and a charge of 1.5 pC.

These are two recent examples of a HG compact S-band linac design in the range of the 140 MeV showing a good compromise from the point of view of performance, cost (industrial supplier) and compactness.

4.2 C-BAND LINACS

One possible option to reduce the length of the linacs and hence to go further in the compactness is to use higher RF frequencies, in this sense an **optimized C-band linac** is being developed for VHEE applications in the range of ~ 100 MeV by the INFN-Sapienza University of Rome. The design is based on a Standing Wave (SW) magnetic coupled bi-periodic structure which has 27 accelerating

Figure 25: C-band linacs HG SW wave accelerating structure.

cells, see figure 25. This design is the result of an optimized scaling of a S-band linac recently developed for FLASH Low-Energy (7 MeV, 100 mA macropulse beam current) experiments and installed at the Institut Curie in Orsay-France. Used in a “warm technology configuration”, i.e. copper linac operated at room temperature, 33 MeV/m could be achieved with 40 MW input RF power (ELI-NP C-band structures). At low-beam current 100 MeV could be achieved with 2 structures (3.6 m), at high-beam current (100 mA) 80 MeV are

achievable. If we use similar structures with a “cold or cryo technology”, i.e. copper linac operated at liquid nitrogen (77K), the nominal gradient is increased until 120 MeV/m with 40 MW input RF power (SLAC technique described in section 3).

4.3 X-BAND LINACS

Going further in the quest for linac compactness by using higher RF frequencies is the application of the **X-band structures** developed in the framework of the CLIC project. The CLIC klystron-based RF Acceleration unit is a 2m long and 1 A beam current structure with a 160 MeV energy gain (see Figure 26).

Figure 26: X-band HG CLIC klystron based basic accelerating RF structure unit.

Using this klystron-based accelerating CLIC unit the CLIC-RF group at CERN in collaboration with the CHUV of Lausanne is developing a linac VHEE RT facility for FLASH in the range of 100 MeV. A basic schematic of the linac is shown in Figure 27. Different linac options with only X-band or combining with S-band at the lower energies are being studied. A preliminary design of a complete facility with some rough dimension using this linac is sketched in Figure 28 (see also Figure 10).

The technical details of such a project are under a confidential agreement between CERN and CHUV and no other information is public at the moment.

Figure 27: Basic schematic and possible options of a X-band and X-band / S-band combined linac based on CLIC klystron RF unit.

Figure 28: Preliminary design of FLASH facility for CHUV Lausanne.

Using also X-bands structures developed by the SLAC laboratory (Section 3), a second generation of the PHASER (Pluridirectional High-energy Agile Scanning electronic Radiotherapy) for electrons with energy ranging from 80-150 MeV is also being studied. A sketch of this facility is shown in Figure 29.

Figure 29: PHASER facility sketch for 80-150 MeV high-energy

5. Conclusion and Perspectives

Many challenges, both technological and biological, have to be addressed and overcome for the ultimate goal of using VHEE and VHEE-FLASH as an innovative modality for effective cancer treatment with minimal damage to healthy tissues. From the accelerator technology point of view an important point is to assess the possibility of focusing and scanning transversely the beam, thereby overcoming the disadvantages associated in the past with low energy electron and photon beam irradiation. Stability, reliability and repeatability are other mandatory ingredients for accelerators to be operated in a medical environment.

The major challenge for VHEE-FLASH is the delivery of very high dose-rate, possibly over a large area, providing a uniform dose distribution throughout the target. Also the parameter window in which the FLASH effect takes place has still to be thoroughly defined, as well as its effectiveness as a function of the physical parameters of the electron beam. This, together with a clear understanding of the underlying biological processes will likely prove to be essential in order to fully optimize the FLASH RT technique. Finally, of particular importance, is the development of reliable on-line dosimetry for very high dose rates, a regime not adapted to the current standard dosimetry techniques for RT. Ionization chambers, routinely used in medical linacs, suffer from nonlinear effects at very high dose rates, and in order to get reliable measurements R&D is needed to develop novel ion chamber types, or explore alternative possibilities as solid state detectors or the use of calibrated beam diagnostics.

All this asks for a large beam test activity, in order to experimentally characterize VHEE beams and their ability to produce the FLASH effect, and provide a test bed for the associated technologies. It is also important to compare the properties of the electron beams depending on the way they are produced, (RF linac or LPA technologies). A number of experimental test facilities are already or in the next future available to perform these ambitious objectives: the CERN Linear Electron Accelerator for Research (CLEAR), so far rather unique in being able to provide both high-energy (50-250 MeV) and high-charge beams, VELA-CLARA at Daresbury, AWA at ANL, PITZ at DESY

and finally ELBE-HZDR using the SC RF technology at Dresden. Further radiobiology studies with LPA electron beams are currently being performed at the DRACO PetaWatt laser facility in ELBE Center at HZDR- Dresden or in the LOA at IPP.

Regarding the linac design in the energy range of interest for VHEE applications there are different possibilities offering the desired performances and compactness with different degrees of technology maturity. The S-band technology is the most mature one, HG compact linacs of this type are already available from various industrial partners. The C-band and X-band RF linacs are still less mature and are mainly constructed in the labs with the help of industries for the machining. In these last times a considerable effort is being made from the industrialization point of view. Furthermore future facilities as exemplified by the CERN-CHUV facility or the upgraded PHASER proposal at SLAC are also on the horizon. In summary an important R&D effort to apply these technologies in the medical is ongoing and if successful could be a step further in the quest for compact and efficient VHEE RT in the range of hundred MeV.

For achieving these aims, a synergistic and multidisciplinary research effort based on accelerator technology as well as physical and radiobiological comparisons to see how well VHEE can meet the current assumptions and become a clinical reality is needed. From the point of view of the accelerator technology the ARIES project is the ideal framework.

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